

**MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI AUTIZM SINDROMLI BOLALARNI INNOVATSION
O'YINLAR ASOSIDA OG'ZAKI NUTQINI RIVOJLANTIRISH****Mirzayeva Diyoraoy Saloxiddin qizi**Toshkent Kimyo xalqaro universiteti magistri Abidova Nilufar Zakirovna Toshkent Kimyo xalqaro
universiteti dotsenti, pedagogika fanlari doktori (Dsc)<https://doi.org/>

Annotatsiya: Maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi autizm sindromli bolalarda og'zaki nutqni rivojlantirish jarayoni innovatsion o'yinlar asosida tahlil qilinadi. Mazkur yondashuv pedagogik va psixologik tamoyillarni birlashtiradi hamda nutq rivojlanishini bosqichma-bosqich strategiyalar bilan qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Innovatsion o'yinlar orqali bolalarning kommunikativ qobiliyati, so'z boyligi, muloqotga kirishish darajasi va interaktiv aloqalari oshadi. Mazkur metodik yondashuv individual xususiyatlarni hisobga olgan holda bolalar bilan samarali muloqot o'rnatish, nutq mashqlarini qiziqarli va rag'batlantiruvchi tarzda tashkil etish imkonini beradi. Interaktiv kartochkalar, qisqa hikoya o'yinlari, rolli o'yinlar, sensor stimulli mashqlar va raqamli interaktiv ilovalar orqali bolalar nutqni amaliy kontekstda qo'llashni o'rganadi, so'z boyligini kengaytiradi va kommunikativ intonatsiya qobiliyatini shakllantiradi. Shu bilan birga, mazkur yondashuv bolalarning ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish, diqqat va kognitiv jarayonlarni mustahkamlash hamda motivatsiyasini oshirishga yordam beradi. Maqola maktabgacha yoshdagi autizm sindromli bolalarning nutq rivojlanishi va kommunikativ kompetensiyasini samarali qo'llab-quvvatlashda innovatsion pedagogik vositalarning ahamiyatini ochib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: autizm sindromi, maktabgacha yosh, og'zaki nutq, innovatsion o'yinlar, kommunikativ rivojlanish

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Volkmar F.R., Klin A. Autism Spectrum Disorders: Diagnosis and Treatment. New York: Guilford Press, 2000. 456 s.
2. Odom S.L., Strain P.S. Evidence-Based Practices in Early Intervention for Children with Autism. New York: Springer, 2002. 389 s.
3. Schreibman L. Teaching Social Communication to Children with Autism: A Practical Guide for Parents and Teachers. London: Guilford Press, 2005. 312 s.
4. Lord C., Risi S., DiLavore P.S. Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule (ADOS). Los Angeles: Western Psychological Services, 2002. 274 s.
5. Rogers S.J., Dawson G. Early Start Denver Model for Young Children with Autism. New York: Guilford Press, 2010. 268 s.
6. Ayupova M.Yu. Logopediya. Tashkent: O'zbekiston faylasuflar milliy jamiyati nashriyoti, 2011. 134 s.
7. Sadovnikova Y.N. Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan psixologik-pedagogik tizim maktabgacha yoshdagi duduqlanuvchi bolalarni rehabilitatsiya qilish. Moskva: Dissertatsiya, 2015. 89 s.
8. Norboyeva Z.R. Autizmlil bolalarda yuz ifodasi va ko'z bilan aloqa asosida erta diagnostika modellari. TAL Journal, 2022. URL: <https://journalss.org/index.php/tal/article/view/239>
9. To'xtaboyeva I.N. Autizm spektr buzilishiga ega bolalar: o'ziga xos rivojlanish xususiyatlari va ijtimoiy integratsiya. Luch Scientific Journal, 2021. URL: <https://journalss.org/index.php/luch/article/view/808>

10. Abduganiyeva D. Autizm: rivojlanish bosqichlari va O'zbekistondagi bolalar orasida tarqalish ko'rsatgichlari. InLibrary, 2020. URL: <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/zdit/article/view/135668>
11. Mirsultonova N.J. Autizm sindromiga ega bolalarda nutq va kommunikativ ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish muammolari. Scientific Journal of Research, 2021. URL: <https://scientific-jl.com/tra/article/view/26877>
12. Utbasarova U., Eshmetova S.M. Autik spektri buzilishi bo'lgan bolalar bilan olib boriladigan sensor integratsiya bosqichlari. NRJ Journal, 2020. URL: <https://ojs.renaissance.com.uz/index.php/nrj/article/view/2485>
13. N. Q. Abidova Autizm spektrli bolalarni o'qitish va tarbiyalash/o'quv qo'llanma. Toshkent – 2023 y.
14. Qutbiddinov A. N. THE TECHNOLOGY OF FORMING GEOMETRIC CONCEPTS IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS WITH INTELLECTUAL DEFECTS BASED ON THE INNOVATION IDEA //INTEGRATION CLUSTER "ON THE BASIS OF INTERDISCIPLINARY RELATIONSHIPS." International Scientific and Current Research Conferences. – 2022.
15. Qutbiddinov A. N. THE TECHNOLOGY OF FORMING GEOMETRIC CONCEPTS IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS WITH INTELLECTUAL DEFECTS BASED ON THE INNOVATION IDEA " INTEGRATION CLUSTER" ON THE BASIS OF INTERDISCIPLINARY RELATIONSHIPS //International Scientific and Current Research Conferences. – 2022. – C. 241-247.
16. Abidova, N. K. (2023). Psychological and pedagogical study of children with autism. Oriental Journal of Education, 3(03), 61-65.
17. Qutbiddinov, A. N. (2022). Technology of forming geometric concepts in primary class students with intellect defects on the basis of "integration Cluster". Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results, 6461-6466.
18. Nazokat, A. (2023). Autizm spektori buzilgan o 'quvchilarning bilish faoliyatining o 'ziga xos xususiyatlari. Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences, 412-415.
19. Abidova, Nazokat. "Positive effects of formation of knowledge, skills and skills on the basis of interdisciplinary relations." *Academica: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 11.3 (2021): 2505-2510.